

On Numbers That Are Pseudo-Smarandache And Smarandache Perfect

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In a paper that is scheduled to be published in volume 31(3) of *Journal of Recreational Mathematics*, entitled "On A Generalization of Perfect Numbers"[1], Joseph L. Pe defines a generalization of the definition of perfect numbers. The standard definition is that a number n is perfect if it is the sum of its proper divisors.

$$n = \sum_{i=1}^k d_i$$

Pe expands this by applying a function to the divisors. Therefore, a number n is said to be **f-perfect** if

$$n = \sum_{i=1}^k f(d_i)$$

for f an arithmetical function.

The Pseudo-Smarandache function is defined in the following way:

For any integer $n \geq 1$, the value of the Pseudo-Smarandache function $Z(n)$ is the smallest integer m such that $1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + m$ is evenly divisible by n .

This function was examined in detail in [2].

The purpose of this paper is to report on a search for numbers that are Pseudo-Smarandache and Smarandache perfect.

A computer program was written to search for numbers that are Pseudo-Smarandache perfect. It was run up through 1,000,000 and the following three Pseudo-Smarandache perfect numbers were found.

$n = 4$ factors 1, 2
 $n = 6$ factors 1, 2, 3
 $n = 471544$ factors 1, 2, 4, 8, 58943, 117886, 235772

This leads to several additional questions:

- a) Are there any other Pseudo-Smarandache perfect numbers?
- b) If the answer to part (a) is true, are there any that are odd?
- c) Is there any significance to the fact that the first three nontrivial factors of the only large number are powers of two?

The Smarandache function is defined in the following way:

For any integer $n > 0$, the value of the Smarandache function $S(n)$ is the smallest integer m such that n evenly divides m factorial.

A program was also written to search for numbers that are Smarandache perfect. It was run up through 1,000,000 and only one solution was found.

$n = 12$ factors - 1, 2, 3, 4, 6

This also leads to some additional questions:

- d) Are there any other Smarandache perfect numbers?
- e) If the answer to part (a) is true, are there any that are odd?
- f) Is there any significance to the fact that n has the first three nontrivial integers as factors?

References

1. Joseph L. Pe, "On a Generalization of Perfect Numbers", *Journal of Recreational Mathematics*, 31(3) to appear.
2. Kenichiro Kashihara, *Comments and Topics on Smarandache Notions and Problems*, Erhus University Press, 1996.